

PROJECT DETAILS

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Executive Summary

This guide constitutes **Deliverable D5.1** of the RIGOR-MED project, led by **Agresta S. Coop.** in collaboration with the **University of Florence**. It establishes the methodological foundation and practical protocol for the **visual photointerpretation of forest disturbances** using high-resolution satellite imagery within Mediterranean ecosystems.

Developed as part of the project's validation phase, the guide defines a **standardized, objective procedure** to ensure consistent, unbiased classification of disturbances such as clear cuts, fires, pest outbreaks, windthrow, and others. Interpretation is conducted through the **Collect Earth Online (CEO) platform**, supported by multi-sensor imagery (Landsat, Sentinel-2, PlanetScope) from 2000 to 2023 and analytical tools like NDVI time series (Geo-Dash)..

By detailing classification criteria, data entry standards, and quality control procedures, Deliverable D5.1 plays a central role in the creation of a **statistically rigorous reference database**, essential for validating both internal and external disturbance products. It directly supports RIGOR-MED's broader goals of enhancing forest monitoring and contributing to an open-access validation resource for European forest dynamics.

1. Introduction

As part of our collaboration with the University of Florence, we have adopted the protocol originally developed by their research team as the foundation for our study. However, we have implemented adaptations to tailor it to our specific needs, particularly incorporating the use of CEO (Collect Earth Online) as a central component of our methodological approach.

The primary goals of the photointerpretation process are to:

- 1) Provide information about the forest disturbance throughout Europe
- 2) Create a multi-temporal database documenting forest disturbance
- 3) Serve as the basis for calculating the final area estimates of the different forest disturbance types

Satellite imagery offers valuable environmental context for the 250m x 250m cells selected for photointerpretation. With adequate structural detail, these images enable the identification of spatially explicit data regarding changes in forest cover over time. A key advantage of satellite-based photointerpretation lies in its ability to detect and delineate forest disturbances that are difficult to identify otherwise. After photointerpretation, a sample of cells will be selected to perform field surveys. However, in most areas, field surveys will not be conducted. In such cases, photointerpretation plays a particularly important role for assessing the status and evolution of the forest landscape over time.

To support the photointerpretation process, several datasets from various satellite sensors were used:

- Landsat: European BAP 1998-2023
- Sentinel-2: BAP 2017-2023 in a buffer area per each cell
- PlanetScope on-demand. Collaboration with PlanetScope is under development. Through an identifying account users will be able to access Planet imagery directly within the CEO interface, filtered according to their specific needs.

2. Project Explanation

2.1. Procedure

The interpretation process is conducted within the CEO (Collect Earth Online) platform using satellite images from Landsat, Sentinel-2, and PlanetScope, the latter available on demand via a registered account. Within each 250m x 250m cell, forest disturbance polygons occurred between 2000 and 2023 are delineated and described. The interpretation is based on an extended viewing quadrat (at least 4000x4000 m) (note: Landsat image tiles are 1,650m x 1,650m, which may affect this interpretation frame). Each polygon of forest disturbance, entirely or partly included in the quadrat, is described

Delineation is guided by visually distinguishable disturbance boundaries. Each delineated polygon is described according to key forest disturbance attributes.

Given the multi-temporal nature of this methodology, the use of the most accurate satellite data is recommended. As such, only Landsat data are available for the years between 2000 and 2023. As of 2017, the occurrence of forest disturbances can also be verified based on Sentinel-2 images. Starting from 2016 Planet scope images are sufficiently spread out and available (fragmentary data and early versions available from previous years), providing higher resolution data. Through API integration, users can verify disturbance timing and type with greater confidence.

All visible disturbance polygons must be mapped following established guidelines on minimum mapping units (MMU) and minimum mapping widths (MMW), which vary according to sensor resolution:

- Landsat (30m x 30m pixels): MMU ~0.1 ha (1000 m² or approx. 32 x 32 m on the ground); MMW = 30 m.
- Sentinel-2 (10m x 10m pixels): MMU = 500 m² (5 pixels); MMW = 10 m.
- PlanetScope (3m x 3m pixels): MMU = 100 m² (approx. 11 pixels); MMW = 10 m.

Smaller disturbances may still be mapped and later evaluated.

Each polygon must be classified based on the following variables:

- Disturbance Type: Clear cut, forest fire, pest, windthrow, or other.
- Year of Occurrence: Between 2000 and 2023.
- Disturbance Magnitude: Rated on a scale of 1–5.
- Forest Recovery Time (Y2R): Number of years to recover 80% of original vegetation.
- Satellite Source: Landsat (LT), Sentinel-2 (S2), or PlanetScope (PS)

Photointerpretation is performed for each survey year, enabling detecting and monitoring changes in the same cells over time.

Figure 1. Project scheme.

2.2. Data to Fill In

The questionnaire must be completed only after **thoroughly analyzing the available satellite imagery** and the corresponding **drawing** of an appropriate geometry—either a **point** or a **polygon**—over the affected area.

Once the geometry is established, the **form** should be filled out. First a response field called **Change** must be filled:

- **Change:** This field confirms whether any change has occurred in the plot between the years 2000 and 2023. The user must select either YES or NO.

Based on the responses provided, **additional fields** may appear to capture further relevant information.

When the answer to **Change** is YES, these response fields include:

- **Disturbance Type (Distu_Type):** This field identifies the nature of the observed disturbance. There are five principal categories:
 - o **Clear Cut (CC):** Includes full tree canopy removal (clear cutting), as well as related subtypes:
 - **Thinning:** Partial removal of trees (must be noted as “Thinning, X%” in the Note field)

- **Road construction**
 - **Firebreaks (Firewall)**
 - **Group selection cutting**
 - **Any other canopy-reducing activity**
 - **Clarification:** *These Subtypes must be logged under the CC category but must also be described using standard keywords in the **Note field** explained below. See section 4 for more details*
- **Forest Fire (FF):** Areas affected by fire events. May vary in intensity and spatial coverage.
 - **Pest (PE):** Damage caused by biotic factors such as insects or disease, typically gradual.
 - **Windthrow (WI):** Tree fall or damage due to strong winds.
 - **Other (OT):** Any disturbance not fitting the categories above, such as: Landslides, Brush clearing, Grass and bush clearing, Forest-to-crop conversion.
- **Disturbance Magnitude (Distu_Mag):** This field assesses the intensity of the disturbance within the polygon. Clear-cutting, due to the complete removal of forest canopy, is typically assigned the highest value (level 5). Less intensive practices, such as thinning or coppicing—where some tree cover remains—are assigned lower values. This same logic applies to fire-related events: large-scale fires that fully destroy forest stands are rated with higher values (e.g., 4–5), while surface-level fires that only partially affect vegetation are rated lower (e.g., 2–3). All magnitude values are based on photointerpretation of satellite imagery, which may vary in resolution. To improve accuracy, analysts are encouraged to examine images from both before and after the disturbance. Still, the final magnitude rating will remain inherently subjective.
 - **Year of Change (Init_Year):** This field captures the year in which the disturbance took place
 - **Years to Recovery (Y2R):** his value represents the number of years needed for the polygon to recover 80% of its vegetation activity following a disturbance. If a second disturbance occurs before the area has fully recovered from the first, the Y2R for the initial event must be set to 0. The Y2R for the second event should then indicate the number of years required for the vegetation to recover from the state it was in at the start of that second event. In cases where the first disturbance affects a substantially larger area and the second only a small portion (for example, 20% or less), the Y2R for the first disturbance should reflect the time needed for the full area to recover. The second Y2R should be calculated independently, based solely on the recovery of the specific area impacted.
 - **Satellite:** This field indicates the primary satellite sensor used to detect the disturbance—either S2 (**Sentinel-2**), LT (**Landsat**), or PS (**PlanetScope**). While additional sensors may be

used for verification, only the sensor used to initially identify the change should be recorded.

- **Note:** This optional field allows users to add relevant observations about the plot to clarify or qualify the interpretation. Use this field especially when:
 - o Visual evidence is subtle or borderline
 - o The change type falls within a subclass of the main category (e.g., for CC specify "Thinning, 25%" for Thinning events, "Road", "Firewall", etc.)
 - o Special scenarios apply (e.g., "Small scale", "Large scale", "Brush clearing", "Landslide")
 - o Notes must always be written in English, using standardized terms where applicable. This ensures consistency across all contributors and facilitates reliable data interpretation.

When the answer to the response field **Change** is **NO**, only the **Note** response field will appear.

In summary, the form will follow this structure:

Figure 2. Form structure.

3. Functionality of Collect Earth Online (CEO)

3.1. Tips

For the best performance when using this tool, it is recommended to use the Firefox browser, as it tends to load images faster and encounters fewer issues than Microsoft Edge or Google Chrome.

3.2. Accessing Assigned Projects

To access the platform, go to <https://www.collect.earth>, where the main page of Collect Earth Online (CEO) will open.

To log in, click the Login button in the top-right corner and enter your email and password.

Figure 3. CEO website.

Figure 4. Logging-in.

Once logged in, on the left-hand side of the screen you will see the general projects assigned to you under the section Your Affiliations. Clicking Visit will take you directly to the corresponding project.

Figure 5. CEO general project dashboard.

Inside the general project dashboard, you will find several elements:

- A list of all institutional projects. The color around each name indicates its progress: Red for no plots collected, Yellow for partial completion, and Green for all plots completed.
- A list of available imagery for that institution. You may choose to use some or all of them.
- A list of all institutional users. Administrators can create and update projects and assign imagery, while members can view projects that are visible to the institution.

To begin photointerpretation, simply hover over the project and click to enter.

Figure 6. Accessing a project.

3.3. CEO Configuration

Once you enter a project and before starting the photointerpretation process, an overview screen will appear displaying key project information:

- **Project Overview** (Figure 7): A global image is shown outlining the boundaries of the project and the spatial distribution of the plots to be analyzed.

Figure 7. Overview of the project dashboard, previous to the photointerpretation process.

- **Summary Button** (Figure 8): This feature allows you to view project statistics at a general level and for individual users.

Project Statistics	
-- Total	20
-- Analyzed	0 (0.00%)
-- Partial	0 (0.00%)
-- Unanalyzed	20 (100.00%)
-- Flagged	0 (0.00%)
-- Users Assigned	1
-- Average Collection Time	untimed
My Statistics	
-- Analyzed	0 (0.00%)
-- Unanalyzed	20 (100.00%)
-- Flagged	0 (0.00%)
-- My Average Time	untimed

Figure 8. Overview of Project Statistics.

- **Navigate** (Figure 9): Enables navigation and classification of the plots based on their analysis status.

Figure 9. Options for Project Plot Status.

- **Imagery Options** (Figure 10): This section lets you choose between different imagery sources. You can select **Mapbox images**, which have an unknown capture date, or **Planet images**, which may offer more accurate and timely data.

Figure 10. Available imagery.

To begin photointerpretation, click the **Go to first plot** button (Figure 11):

The screenshot shows a web interface for 'Test plots FRAMEWORK_SWIR'. At the top, there is a teal header with an information icon and the title. Below the header, there is a 'Navigate' dropdown menu currently set to 'Analyzed plots'. Underneath, the 'Mode' section has two radio buttons: 'Collect' (which is selected) and 'Admin Review'. A prominent blue arrow points to the 'Go to first plot' button, which is highlighted in teal. Below this is the 'Imagery Options' section, featuring a dropdown menu set to 'Mapbox Satellite' and an unchecked checkbox for 'Enable Map Grid'. The 'Survey Questions' section is partially visible, showing a message: 'Please go to a plot to see survey questions'. At the bottom of the interface is a 'Quit' button.

Figure 11. Beginning Photointerpretation.

From this point on, **two windows** will open simultaneously:

- **Main page:** Includes the form, drawing tools, and Planet images, this is your main working interface.
- **Geo-Dash page:** Provides access to NDVI time series and data from Landsat and Sentinel-2, enabling more detailed analysis of plot changes.

3.3.1. Main Page

The **Main Page** (Figure 12) of Collect Earth Online (CEO) is the central interface used during the photointerpretation process. It integrates all essential tools, imagery, and forms required to analyze assigned plots.

You can switch between different satellite image sources at any time and consult overall or user-specific project statistics directly from this page

Figure 12. Overview of the Main Page of a Project.

3.3.1.1. Navigating Between Plots

To move between plots, you have two main options (Figure 13):

- **Navigation Arrows** – Use these to move through plots sequentially.
- **Plot ID Search** – Enter the specific ID of a plot to access it directly.

Figure 13. Tools for navigating between plots.

Plot Status Indicators

Each plot is assigned one of the following status labels (Figure 9):

- **Assigned** – Default state when a plot is allocated.
- **Unanalyzed** – Indicates that the plot has not been reviewed.
- **Analyzed** – The plot has been fully reviewed and saved.
- **Flagged** – Marked for review due to insufficient data or interpretation uncertainty.

Navigation Behavior Based on Plot Status

When navigating between plots, it's important to consider the **active status filter**. **Navigation arrows** will only move you through plots that match the currently selected status. For example, if the **"Unanalyzed"** filter is active, the arrows will only cycle through unanalyzed plots.

Similarly, if you attempt to search for the ID of a plot that has a different status (e.g., **"Analyzed"** or **"Flagged"**) while the **"Unanalyzed"** filter is active, the system will not return any results. To locate such plots, you must first change the active filter to the appropriate status category.

3.3.1.2. External Tools

Several external tools are available to support the photointerpretation process (Figure 14):

Figure 14. External Tools.

- **Re-zoom:** This tool allows you to quickly zoom back in on the plot in case you have zoomed out too far.
- **GeoDash:** One of the most important tools. If the GeoDash panel has been accidentally closed, this button will reopen it immediately.
- **Hide Samples:** Hides the sample markers (central points) from the working interface.
- **Hide Boundary:** Conceals the rectangle that outlines the study plot, allowing for a clearer view of the surrounding area.
- **Download Plot KML:** Allows you to download the plot as a KML or KMZ file, which can be viewed in Google Earth.
- **Interpretation Instructions:** Displays specific instructions provided by the administrator to assist in interpreting the plot correctly.

3.3.1.3. Survey Questions

The Survey Questions section is the **most critical part of the CEO** interface. It is where all plot-specific information is entered, based on the geometries you define. Completing the form involves **two essential steps**:

1. Drawing the Geometry

Before completing the form, you must first define a geometry—either a point or a polygon—depending on the type and extent of the disturbance observed. Each geometry is automatically linked to its own dedicated form, meaning that the number of forms within a plot corresponds directly to the number of geometries created. **One form must be completed for each geometry.**

- To begin, click the pencil icon to enter drawing mode and choose the appropriate tool:
 - **Point Tool** (Figure 15): Select this option and on the main image to place the point.

- To **move a point**: enter drawing mode by clicking on the **pencil icon** , select the **Point tool icon**, hold CTRL, hover over the point (the system will assist in selecting it), then left-click and drag. Release to place it.
- To **delete a point**: follow the same steps as to move it, but right-click instead of left-clicking.

Figure 15. Example of point drawing.

- **Polygon Tool** (Figure 16): click multiple times on the image to define the vertices. Complete the shape by clicking the first vertex again or letting the system auto-close.
 - To **modify a polygon**: enter drawing mode by clicking on the **pencil icon** , select the **Polygon tool icon**, hold CTRL, hover over the vertex you want to move, then left-click and drag. Release to place it.
 - To **delete a polygon**: use the same steps as to modify it, but right-click instead of left-clicking.

Figure 16. Example of polygon drawing.

2. Completing the Form

Once a geometry is drawn, click the question mark icon to open the associated form.

- Start answering with the “**Change**” field, which asks whether a disturbance occurred between 2000 and 2023. Select **Yes** or **No** and click the **Save** button corresponding to this specific field.
- Depending on your answer, the additional fields that appear differ (Figure 2):
 - If **Yes** (Figure 17), the additional **fields** appearing are:
 - **Disturbance Type** (Distu_Type)
 - **Disturbance Magnitude** (Distu_Mag)
 - **Year of Change** (Init_Year)
 - **Years to Recovery** (Y2R)
 - **Satellite**
 - **Note**
 - If **No**, only the **Note** field appears.
- Fill out the first response field that appears, called **Change**. This field confirms whether any change has occurred in the plot between the years 2000 and 2023. The user must select either YES or NO. Select the corresponding answer and then click the Save button corresponding to this response field.
- Once the field **Change is** answered and saved, based on the response provided **additional** subsequent **fields** capturing further relevant information unlock:
 - When the answer to **Change** is YES (Figure 17), the response fields that appear are **Disturbance Type (Distu_Type), Disturbance Magnitude (Distu_Mag), Year of Change (Init_Year), Years to Recovery (Y2R), Satellite** and **Note**.
 - When the answer to the response field **Change** is NO, only the **Note** response field will appear.

Enable Map Grid

Survey Questions

Unanswered Color Black White

1

Change?

YES NO

- Distu type

CC OT

FF WI

PET

- Distu mag

4 5

- Init year

2005 Save

- V2R

0 Save

- Satellite

LT PS

- Note

- Save

1

Flag Plot Clear All

Save Quit

Figure 17. Example of response fields appearing when the answer to **Change** is YES.

- Each field must be saved individually by clicking its corresponding Save button (Figure 18). Saved fields turn blue, while unsaved ones remain red (Figure 18).
- Once all fields are completed and saved, click the final **Save** button at the bottom of the form page to store the full form submission (Figure 17).
- If any required field remains unsaved, an error message will notify you, preventing form submission.

- To **modify a saved response**:
 - Select the relevant geometry.
 - Update the answer in the specific field.
 - Click the **Save** button corresponding to the specific field again.
- When working with **multiple polygons in the same plot**, it is essential to **reselect the relevant polygon before saving each response field**.
 - The process is as follows:
 - First, select **one polygon**, complete the **first response** field associated with it, and click the corresponding **Save** button. Then, **reselect** the same polygon, **fill** in the **second response** field, and **save** again. Repeat these steps for each field linked to that polygon.
 - Once all fields for that polygon are saved, move on to the next polygon and repeat the process. After completing and saving all responses for all polygons, click the **Save** button at the bottom of the form page (Figure 17) to register all entries linked to the plot.
 - **Important**: Failing to reselect the appropriate polygon before saving may result in errors that prevent form submission and could require you to delete and redraw all geometries.
 - **Note**: If only one polygon is present, it is automatically selected, and no manual reselection is needed.
- **Additional Form Controls**: At the bottom of the form, you'll find these options (Figure 17):
 - **Flag Plot** – Marks a plot as **unassessable** due to **missing**, **poor-quality**, or **unusable** imagery. After selecting the **Flag Plot** option, a **mandatory text** field will appear. You must provide a clear **justification** in this field and **save** the response.
 - **Clear All** – Deletes all responses for the current plot.
 - **Save** – Stores the complete form once all fields are filled and saved.
 - **Quit** – Exits the project and returns to the CEO dashboard.

Figure 18. Example of an unsaved response (left) and a saved one (right) in the Y2R response field.

Once the form is successfully saved (via the “**Save**” button at the end of the form), or Flagged (via the “**Flag Plot**” button at the end of the form), the platform will automatically advance you to the next plot for analysis.

3.3.2. Geo-Dash

The Geo-Dash panel is a pop-up window that offers a broader, temporal view of each plot's condition. It displays the full set of available imagery and vegetation indices to support photointerpretation. It includes:

- An **NDVI (Normalized Difference Vegetation Index) time series** from 1998 to 2024.

- **Landsat** images from 1998 to 2023.
- **Sentinel-2** images from 2017 to 2023.

Figure 19. Overview of the Geo-Dash interface.

General Functionality

A **Mapbox image** functions as the **base layer beneath** the Landsat and Sentinel-2 imagery. Since the capture **date** of the Mapbox image is **unknown**, it may not be temporally aligned with the overlaid satellite data—an important factor to consider during interpretation.

To **compare** changes observed in the **Landsat** or **Sentinel-2** imagery with the underlying **Mapbox base image**, use the **slider bar** to adjust the transparency from right to left (Figure 20).

Figure 20. Use of the slider to compare images.

If you zoom out too far, click the crosshair symbol to recenter and zoom into the plot automatically.

Clicking the **four-arrows symbol** enlarges the selected image to full-screen view.

3.3.2.1. NDVI Time Series

This time series represents NDVI values for the plot between 1998 and 2024.

Figure 21. General view of the NDVI time series.

At the top of the interface, a **Mapbox base image** is displayed with an **unknown capture date**, accompanied by a frame that outlines the study plot.

The **NDVI time series** serves as a useful reference for detecting changes or confirming suspected ones. However, if a change appears in the time series in **November 2007**, but is clearly visible in **Landsat imagery in 2008**, the official year of change should be recorded as **2008**, even if the change may have begun earlier.

The same guideline applies to **Google Earth imagery**. Additionally, if a change is visible **only** in the NDVI time series and Google Earth **but not in satellite imagery** like Landsat or Sentinel-2, it **should not be recorded**.

Interpretation of the Time Series

Beneath the **Mapbox base image**, the **NDVI time series** is displayed as a sequence of **blue dots** (Figure 21), each representing a different satellite image of the plot with its associated **date** and **classification**.

The axes of the NDVI time series chart are interpreted as follows:

- **Vertical axis:** Represents NDVI values, which may vary depending on the scale used.
- **Horizontal axis:** Indicates the image capture date. When hovering over a point, the exact date is displayed (Figure 22).

Figure 22. NDVI chart showing vertical and horizontal axes.

The **NDVI values**, represented by blue dots, can be **interpreted** as:

- **Values near 1** → Indicate dense vegetation cover, such as forests or healthy vegetation.

Figure 23. Example of NDVI time series for stable forest.

- **Values near 0** → Indicate sparsely vegetated or bare areas, such as exposed soil, rock, or grasslands.

Figure 24. Example of NDVI time series for grassland.

- **Values below 0** → Correspond to water surfaces, snow, or cloud cover. Clicking on a point will display the corresponding NDVI image in the upper section of the interface, where you can zoom in and out.

Figure 25. Example of NDVI time series for a water body.

These values offer key insights into vegetation dynamics, as different land cover types show distinct temporal patterns (Figure 26).

Figure 26. Example of NDVI time series showing clear cuts in 2014 and 2016.

Viewing NDVI Images

When clicking on a point in the time series, the corresponding NDVI image will be displayed above.

- You can zoom in or out for a more detailed analysis.
- You can choose between **different Band Combinations**: The Map Bands field (Figure 27) allows users to switch between three different spectral band combinations, facilitating the interpretation of vegetation and land cover conditions using distinct reflectance characteristics.

Figure 27. Available Map Bands combinations.

3.3.2.2. Landsat Imagery

The available Landsat imagery covers the period from 1998 to 2023. As with the NDVI time series, users can zoom in and out for detailed visual inspection.

Landsat images are typically visualized using the **NIR (Near Infrared)**, **SWIR1 (Short-Wave Infrared 1)**, and **RED band** combination. This spectral setup is especially useful for identifying vegetation health, moisture content, and land cover types. In general:

- **Dark red tones** often indicate dense, healthy vegetation with high moisture content and chlorophyll activity, typically found in dense well-established forests. The high reflectance in the NIR band—due to internal leaf structure—and low absorption in the RED band enhance this effect.
- **Orange to green transitions** suggest lower vegetation density or reduced moisture levels. These colors are commonly associated with **shrublands, grasslands, or partially vegetated areas**. However, the exact tone can also be influenced by:
 - Chlorophyll concentration: Lower levels yield less NIR reflectance and more RED reflectance, shifting colors toward orange or yellow.
 - Vegetation type and structure: Different species and leaf arrangements affect spectral response.
 - Phenological stage: Young growth vs. senescent vegetation can shift tone.
 - Soil background: Sparse vegetation allows more soil signal to dominate, especially in dry or sandy areas.
- **Light green or beige tones** may appear in cultivated fields or partially disturbed areas, depending on crop type, growth phase, or residue cover.
- **Grayish areas** typically represent urban surfaces, exposed rocks, or highly compacted bare soil.
- **Dark blue to black tones** are characteristic of water bodies, which strongly absorb in the NIR and SWIR bands, yielding low reflectance values.

Below are examples of typical plot types and their associated spectral signatures:

- **Forested areas:** The color tones observed will vary depending on the density of the forest canopy. In areas with very dense vegetation, the imagery typically displays deep **reddish** hues, which are easily identifiable. As the tree density decreases to moderate or sparse, the colors gradually shift from reddish-orange to greenish tones, reflecting a reduced level of forest cover.

Figure 28. Example of Landsat imagery for dense forest.

Figure 29. Example of Landsat imagery for a sparse forest.

- **Shrubland:** Typically appears in **dark green** or **brownish tones**, often with **reddish-brown** variations, depending on the vegetation type and its density.

Figure 30. Example of Landsat imagery showing tall shrubland.

Figure 31. Example of Landsat imagery showing low shrubland.

- **Grassland:** Usually displays **light green** or **yellowish** hues, which vary with the season and the level of moisture available.

Figure 32. Example of Landsat imagery for dry grassland.

- **Bare Soil:** Appears in **light brown, beige,** or **grayish** tones, depending on soil composition and moisture conditions.

Figure 33. Example of Landsat imagery for bare soil.

- **Crops:** During the growing season, cropland is often **bright green** or **yellow**, but may shift to light **brown** or **beige** after harvest.

Figure 34. Example of Landsat imagery for crops.

- **Urban Areas:** Characterized by **gray** tones, which vary depending on construction type and the material of artificial surfaces.

Figure 35. Example of Landsat imagery for urban areas.

- **Water Bodies:** Commonly represented in **blue** or **dark blue** tones, though they may appear **brownish** or **greenish** if affected by turbidity or algae presence.

Figure 36. Example of Landsat imagery for a sea.

Figure 37. Example of Landsat imagery for a river.

Figure 38. Example of Landsat imagery for a reservoir.

- **Forest affected by a Clear-Cutting Disturbance Type** (section 2.2): Forests affected by clear-cutting typically appear in **dark reddish** tones prior to the disturbance. In the year the change occurs, the affected area will exhibit a **clear contrast** in color, depending on the nature of the land cover that replaces the forest—such as **bare soil, grassland, or shrubland**.

Figure 39. Example of Landsat imagery showing a clear cut in 2008 (Disturbance type CC).

Figure 40. Example of Landsat imagery showing a clear cut in 2016 (Disturbance type CC).

When **thinning** occurs—rather than a full clear cut—the initial **dark reddish** tones typically observed before the disturbance begin to fade, gradually shifting toward **reddish-orange** and eventually **greenish** hues. This progression reflects a partial reduction in forest cover, rather than complete canopy removal.

Figure 41. Example of Landsat imagery showing a thinning event in 2011 (Disturbance type CC).

These distinct color patterns are key for correctly identifying and interpreting changes in land cover over time.

3.3.2.3. Sentinel-2 Imagery

Sentinel-2 images are available for the period **2017 to 2023**. As with the NDVI time series, these images can be zoomed in and out for detailed plot analysis.

A key advantage of Sentinel-2 imagery is the application of a **mask that displays only forested and dense shrubland areas**. As a result, features such as croplands, grasslands, bare soil, urban zones, or water bodies are not shown—unless they result from a change originating in previously forested areas.

This imagery is displayed using a **NIR (Near Infrared), SWIR2 (Short-Wave Infrared 2), and RED band combination**, which is particularly useful for analyzing vegetation, detecting soil moisture, and identifying areas affected by fire or degradation. The interpretation of this band combinations is as follows:

- **Dense, healthy vegetation** typically appears in deep red tones, resulting from high reflectance in the NIR band and strong absorption in the red band—a characteristic response of vigorous plant cover.
- **Vegetation under water stress or with reduced density** is generally shown in orange to yellow hues, as the SWIR2 band is sensitive to moisture levels in both vegetation and soil.
- **Bare soils** and **urban areas** are represented in brown, beige, or gray tones, due to low reflectance in the NIR band and a comparatively stronger response in SWIR2.

- **Water bodies** appear in dark blue or black, as water absorbs most of the energy in the infrared spectrum. This response is visually similar to what is seen in Landsat imagery

The following are examples of typical land cover types observed in Sentinel-2 imagery, along with their characteristic color tones and spectral responses:

- **Forested Areas:** Appear in deep or **intense red** tones. Dense, healthy vegetation strongly reflects in the NIR band and absorbs in the RED band, resulting in rich **reddish** coloration.

Figure 42. Example of Sentinel-2 image for forested area.

- **Shrubland:** Typically presents lighter **red, orange, or yellow** hues. These tones reflect lower vegetation density and higher moisture content, which reduce NIR reflectance and shift the visual response toward warmer colors than the ones observed in Forested Areas.

Figure 43. Example of Sentinel-2 image for shrubland.

- **Grasslands:** Display **yellow, orange, or light brown** tones. Lower biomass and fluctuating moisture levels result in intermediate responses in both the NIR and SWIR2 bands, producing softer, warmer colors.

Figure 44. Example of Sentinel-2 image for grassland.

- **Bare Soil:** Typically appears in **beige, brown, or grayish** tones. The absence of vegetation results in low reflectance in the NIR band, while the SWIR2 response varies depending on soil composition and moisture content.

Figure 45. Example: Sentinel-2 image of bare soil.

- **Croplands:** Spectral tones vary from bright green (during active growth) to reddish or brown (in late stages or post-harvest), depending on the crop type and phenological stage. Note: No example image available, but these tones are typical when forested areas are converted to agriculture.
- **Urban Areas:** Shown in **light gray or white tones**. Built surfaces like asphalt and concrete exhibit low NIR reflectance and moderate SWIR2 response, resulting in neutral appearances. Note: No example image available, but these tones apply to forest-to-urban land transitions.
- **Water Bodies:** Represented by **dark blue or black** tones, due to the strong absorption of infrared radiation by water. Note: No example image available, but these colors are typical of forest-to-water transitions.
- **Forests with Canopy Loss:** Transition from dark red to lighter tones—such as orange, yellow, or brown—when affected by disturbances like deforestation, fire, or degradation. In these cases, NIR reflectance decreases, and SWIR2 emphasizes drier, less vegetated areas with lighter or muted tones.

Figure 46. Example: Sentinel-2 imagery of deforested areas in 2023

4. Interpretation Key

This section provides visual and analytical references for classifying forest disturbances using Landsat, Sentinel-2, and Planet imagery. Each disturbance type includes interpretation tips, sample cases, and before/after image comparisons to support consistent photointerpretation across users.

4.1. Clear cut (CC)

The **Clear Cut (CC)** category encompasses a broad range of forest disturbances that result in the **removal of tree cover**, either **fully** or **partially**, within a defined area. While the term **clear cut** traditionally refers to the **complete removal of all trees**, for the purposes of this project, the **CC category also includes several related disturbance types** that cause a significant reduction in canopy cover, **even if the canopy is not fully eliminated**.

The following **disturbance types** are classified under the **CC category**:

- **Complete Clear Cuts:** Total removal of the forest canopy.
- **Thinning:** Partial tree removal that retains some canopy cover.
- **Road Construction:** Full vegetation removal to create roads or access paths.
- **Firebreaks (Firewalls):** Vegetation cleared for fire prevention—often visually similar to roads.
- **Group Selection Harvesting:** Small, circular, and often numerous clearings that completely remove tree cover.
- **Other Interventions:** Any activity involving partial canopy removal within a forested area.

While **complete clear cuts** are visually the most distinct, the other subtypes all result in detectable changes in canopy structure that justify their inclusion under the CC category. To ensure clarity, these cases should be differentiated using the **"Note" field** in the **CEO form**. For example:

- "Thinning, 30%" to indicate partial removal
- "Road" or "Firewall" to specify linear infrastructure clearing
- Any other brief description that distinguishes the disturbance from a full clear cut

This expanded definition ensures that all major structural changes to forested areas are consistently recognized and documented. These disturbances typically produce clear spectral signals in satellite imagery and can be reliably identified through photointerpretation.

Visual Reference Tables

The following **tables** provide visual **examples** to support **consistent identification** of CC subtypes:

- Table 1, Table 2, Table 3 and Table 4: Clear cut examples
- Table 5: Thinning
- Table 6: Road construction
- Table 7: Group selection harvesting

Table 1. Example of Visual Interpretation for the **Clear-Cut** Subcategory (year 2020).

Data source	Clear Cut (CC)	
	BEFORE CHANGE	AFTER CHANGE
Landsat		
Sentinel		
Planet		

Table 2. Example of Visual Interpretation for the **Clear-Cut** Subcategory (year 2018).

Data source	Clear Cut (CC)	
	BEFORE CHANGE	AFTER CHANGE
Landsat		
Sentinel		
Planet		

Table 3. Example of Visual Interpretation for the **Clear-Cut** Subcategory (year 2020).

Data source	Clear Cut (CC)	
	BEFORE CHANGE	AFTER CHANGE
Landsat		
Sentinel		
Planet		

Table 4. Example of Visual Interpretation for the **Clear-Cut** Subcategory (year 2019).

Data source	Clear Cut (CC)	
	BEFORE CHANGE	AFTER CHANGE
Landsat		
Sentinel		
Planet		

Table 5. Example of Visual Interpretation for the **Thinning** Subcategory.

Data source	Thinning (CC)	
	BEFORE CHANGE	AFTER CHANGE
Landsat		
Sentinel		
Planet		

Table 6. Example of Visual Interpretation for the **Road** Subcategory.

Data source	Clear Cut for Road construction (CC)	
	BEFORE CHANGE	AFTER CHANGE
Landsat	<p>Landsat_2021</p>	
Sentinel	<p>Sentinel_2021</p>	
Planet		

Table 7. Example of Visual Interpretation for the **Group selection cutting (CC)** Subcategory.

Data source	Group selection cutting (CC)	
	BEFORE CHANGE	AFTER CHANGE
Landsat		
Sentinel		
Planet		

4.2. Forest Fire (FF)

This category includes all **disturbances** caused by **fire**. One of the **key indicators** is the emergence of **bright fluorescent** green tones in **Sentinel-2** imagery. Landsat imagery may also reflect change, though typically in **darker green** hues.

Table 8. Example Case – **Forest Fire (FF)** in Shrubland (2022).

Data source	Forest Fire (FF)	
	BEFORE CHANGE	AFTER CHANGE
Landsat		
Sentinel		
Planet		

Table 9. Example Case – Large-scale **Forest fire** (2022)

Data source	Forest Fire (FF)	
	BEFORE CHANGE	AFTER CHANGE
Landsat		
Sentinel		
Planet		

4.3. Pest (PE)

Disturbances caused by pests are often **gradual** and **more difficult** to detect than abrupt changes. **Damage** generally becomes **apparent** only when salvage logging follows an outbreak, making it challenging to differentiate from thinning or seasonal variation (phenology).

Table 10. Example – Brown Band Pest (2018). Includes progressive imagery showing gradual vegetation loss across Landsat, Sentinel-2, and Planet.

Data source	Pest (PE)	
Landsat		

Data source	Pest (PE)	
Sentinel	<p>Sentinel_2018</p>	
	<p>Sentinel_2019</p>	
Planet		

Table 11. Time Series – Brown Band Pest (2012–2018). Supplemented by Google Earth imagery for cross-verification.

Data source	Pest (PE)	
Landsat		

Data source	Pest (PE)	
Sentinel	<div style="display: flex; justify-content: space-between;"> <div style="width: 48%;"> <p data-bbox="344 304 488 327">Sentinel_2017</p> </div>	
Planet	<div style="display: flex; justify-content: space-around;"> <div style="width: 48%;"> <p data-bbox="344 983 408 1005">2016</p> </div> </div>	
Google Earth	2014	2017

Data source	Pest (PE)
	<p>2020</p>

4.4. Other (OT)

This category captures **less frequent or miscellaneous disturbance** types that do not fall under the previous classifications. The most common ones are:

- **Landslides:** Naturally occurring slope failures (Table 12).
- **Brush Clearing:** The removal of dense shrubs, often in areas used for grazing, agroforestry or forest-to-crop conversion (Table 13).
- **Grass and Bush Clearing:** The clearing of herbaceous vegetation and scattered shrubs in open landscapes. More frequent and less dense than brush-cleared areas (Table 14 and Table 15).

Table 12. Example: Visual guide for interpreting **Landslides**.

Landslide	Landslide (OT)	
	BEFORE CHANGE	AFTER CHANGE
Landsat		
Sentinel		
Planet		

Table 13. Example: Interpretation of **Brush-cleared land**.

Data source	Brush clearing (OT)	
	BEFORE CHANGE	AFTER CHANGE
Landsat	<p>Landsat_2021</p>	
Sentinel	<p>Sentinel_2021</p>	
Planet		

Table 14. Example: Interpretation of **Bush clearing**.

Data source	Brush clearing (OT)	
	BEFORE CHANGE	AFTER CHANGE
Landsat	<p>Landsat_2022</p>	
Sentinel	<p>Sentinel_2022</p>	
Planet		

Table 15. Example: Visual cues for interpreting **Grass and bush clearing**.

Data source	Grass and bush clearing (OT)	
	BEFORE CHANGE	AFTER CHANGE
Landsat		
Sentinel		
Planet		

5. CEO Form

This section provides a **step-by-step guide** for accurately **completing** the **CEO** (Collect Earth Online) **form** under various scenarios. Each part of the form is explained in detail, with examples and tips to ensure accurate and consistent data entry.

For a **full overview** of form fields and response options, please refer to section **2.2** Data to Fill In

5.1. How to Respond to Plots with No Changes

If you determine that no change has occurred in a plot, follow this protocol:

- Click the pencil icon to enter drawing mode and choose the **Point Tool**
- Place a point in the center of the plot.
- Click the question mark icon to open the associated form.
- Start answering with the **“Change”** field, answer "No" and click the “Save” button for this field.
- Complete the process by filling out the **“Note” field** if necessary, or leave it blank and click “Save”.
- Once all fields are completed and saved, click the final **Save** button at the bottom of the form page to store the full form submission (Figure 47 and/or section 3.3.1.3).
- Remember that each field must be saved individually by clicking its corresponding Save button (Figure 47 and/or section 3.3.1.3). Saved fields turn blue, while unsaved ones remain red (Figure 18 in section 3.3.1.3). If any required field remains unsaved, an error message will notify you, preventing form submission.

Figure 47. Example of Plot with no changes.

5.2. How to Respond to Plots with Changes

If a plot contains visible changes, proceed as follows:

- Click the pencil icon to enter drawing mode and choose the **Polygon Tool**.
- Draw as many polygons as there are distinct changes in the plot (see section 3.3.1.3 for more details). **Each polygon** must **cover the specific area affected by a change**. There will be as many polygons as disturbances identified. If there is more than one change, i.e., more than one polygon:
 - Draw a polygon for the first affected area.
 - Complete and save the form for that polygon.
 - Then draw a new polygon for the next affected area and repeat the process.
 - Once all forms are filled, click the **“Save”** button at the bottom of the form page to store the full form submission (Figure 47). Important: You do not need to save the form after each individual entry. It's sufficient to save it once all responses are complete.
- For every polygon drawn, fill in the form immediately after drawing it. To do so:

- Click the question mark icon to open the associated form.
- Select the polygon.
- Start answering with the **“Change”** field, answer "Yes" and click the **“Save”** button for this field.
- Reselect the polygon and answers and **“Save”** each of the other response fields (Distu_Type, Distu_Mag, Init_Year, Y2R, Satellite y Note). Remember to reselect the polygon each time you answer a response field (See section 3.3.1.3 for more details)

Figure 48. Example of Plot with one change

Figure 49. Example of Plot with two changes.

5.3. How to complete the "Note" section

This section of the form is intended to provide context for the decisions made, clarify uncertainties, record alternative interpretations, or specify the type of disturbance observed.

In most cases, **this section will rarely be used**, as it is not necessary to provide any input when dealing with a "No Change" situation or a common disturbance event (such as deforestation, forest fires, pest or windthrow).

However, in certain situations, it will be essential to document specific characteristics of the plot or the observed disturbance. To ensure consistency and standardization, a set of predefined notes must be used in these cases:

A) Small changes

If minor or barely perceptible changes are observed in Landsat or Sentinel satellite imagery, they must be recorded in the form, and the phrase "**Small scale**" must be entered in the "Note" section. See section 2.2 for more details.

Figure 50. Before and after example of a **small-scale change**.

B) Big changes

If the detected change exceeds the area defined by a 4 km x 4 km square, the polygon should be drawn only up to the boundary of the square. It is not necessary to continue delineating the change beyond this limit, even if the disturbance visibly persists outside the area. In such cases, include the phrase "**Large scale**" in the "**Note**" section. Refer to section 2.2 for more details.

Figure 51. Example of a **Big-scale change** caused by a forest fire in 2018.

Figure 52. Example of a **big-scale change** caused by a forest fire in 2020

C) Thinning

When the **tree cover** is only partially removed, "**Thinning**" must be used, followed by the estimated percentage of canopy loss, for example, "thinning 20%.". Despite the partial removal, these plots must still be classified as "**CC**" (Clear Cut). See section 4.1 or section 2.2 for further details.

Figure 53. Example of before and after a **20% thinning**.

D) Firebreak or Firewall

Firebreaks (or Firewalls) are considered a subtype of **CC** (Clear Cut) and must be classified accordingly. In addition, the term "**Firewall**" must always be entered in the **Note** field to clearly specify the nature of the disturbance. For further details, refer to section 4.1 or section 2.2.

Figure 54. Example of before and after a **Firewall Disturbance**.

E) Roads

When the construction of a **road** is detected, the term "**Road**" must be recorded. If the removed vegetation was **shrubland** or **grassland**, it must have been previously classified as **OT** (Other), and if it was **tree cover**, it must have been classified as **CC** (Clear Cut). For further details, refer to section 4.1 or section 2.2.

Figure 55. Example of before and after a **Road Disturbance**.

F) Group selection cutting

When a group selection cutting is detected (characteristic in Bulgaria, where small circular stands are harvested for research projects), it must be classified as **CC** (Clear Cut), and the term "**Group selection cutting**" must be used in the **Note** field. For further details, refer to section 4.1 or section 2.2.

Figure 56. Example of before and after a **Group selection cutting**.

G) Any other canopy-reducing activity

Any intervention that results in partial canopy removal within a forested area, but does not fit the specific **CC** (Clear Cut) subcategories described, must still be classified as CC. A brief **description distinguishing** the disturbance from a full clear-cut must be provided in the Note field. For more information, refer to section 4.1 or section 2.2.

H) Landslide

In these cases, the term "**Landslide**" must always be recorded, and the event must be previously **classified** under the category **Other** (OT). See section 4.1 or section 2.2 for further details.

Figure 57. Example of before and after a **Landslide event**.

I) Clearing

When vegetation removal affects only **shrubs** or **grasses**—whether within forested areas or forest plantations—the disturbance must be classified as **Other (OT)**. Additionally, a specific annotation in the **Note** field, specifying the **type** of **vegetation** cleared:

- "**Brush clearing**" → Use this term for areas where **dense shrub cover** has been cleared. Refer to Section 4.4 or Section 2.2 for further details.

Figure 58. Example of before and after a brush clearing.

- "**Grass and bush clearing**" → Use this term for more open areas characterized by **grass** and **scattered shrubs** where vegetation removal has occurred. See section 4.4 or section 2.2 for more detail.

Figure 59. Example of before and after a **Grass and Bush clearing**.

5.4. How to complete plots without available imagery

In certain cases, the GeoDash platform may not display Landsat images for every year, as the temporal range of available imagery has been restricted to the months of June, July, and August. As a result, imagery may be missing for certain years (Figure 60).

If imagery is missing for **only a single year**, this will not pose a problem, and the form should be completed following the **standard procedure**. However, if images are missing for **several consecutive years**, the following protocol must be applied:

- Place a point at the center of the plot.
- Complete the form by selecting "No Change" in the Change field.
- In the Note field, write "NA" to indicate missing data.

The year 2012 will be particularly affected regarding image availability, due to the transition between the Landsat 5 and Landsat 7 satellites, which resulted in reduced coverage and a greater number of missing data compared to other years.

Figure 60. Example of a plot with missing Landsat imagery.

5.5. Flag Plots

Flag Plots are plots for which there is **insufficient information** to perform an accurate photointerpretation, or where it is not possible to confidently determine the observed features. This situation may arise for several reasons, such as the **absence of imagery** during the study period or the availability of **low-quality** or **severely degraded** images.

When a plot cannot be reliably interpreted, the following protocol must be followed:

- Do not create any geometry (no points or polygons).
- Scroll to the bottom of the form.
- Select the "Flag Plot" checkbox (Figure 17).

Once the plot is flagged, a mandatory field will appear (Figure 61) where you must clearly justify the reason for flagging the plot, providing a precise explanation the lack of imagery, poor image quality, or other specific difficulties encountered during interpretation. After, the response must be saved by clicking the **Save** button.

Figure 61. Example of a Flag Plot response.

Following, an example of a Flag plot (Figure 62).

Figure 62. Example of contaminated and damaged Landsat images.

6. Data Download

The data **download process** in Collect Earth Online (CEO) can be done within the Project Management Interface (Figure 63) and mainly produces **two** distinct **output files**, each serving a different purpose:

- **SHP File (Shapefile Format):** This file contains the spatial representation of the **mapped geometries (points, polygons)**, but does not include any attribute data from the form responses. It is primarily used to visualize the shapes and locations of delineated disturbances in a GIS environment. This file can be downloaded via the button "**Download Shape Files**" (Figure 63)
- **CSV File:** This file includes all the **form data** entered during the photointerpretation process. When visualized in QGIS or other GIS software, it is displayed as **point data**, with each point representing either the **center of the plot** (when NO CHANGE was documented in the plot) or the **center of a disturbance polygon** (when CHANGE was documented in the plot). This file can be downloaded via the button "**Download Sample Data**" (Figure 63)

The screenshot displays the 'Project Management' interface. On the left, a 'Collection Design' map shows a yellow rectangular Area of Interest (AOI) boundary over a satellite image of the Mediterranean region. Below the map, the 'Imagery Selection' panel shows 'Default Imagery: Mapbox Satellite' and 'Additional Imagery:' is empty. The 'AOI Boundary' panel shows 'Boundary Coordinates' and 'North: 46.383515213'. On the right, the 'Project Management' sidebar shows project details: 'Date Created: 2024-12-04', 'Date Published: 2024-12-04', and 'Date Closed: Open'. It also includes buttons for 'Close Project', 'Edit Project', and 'Delete Project'. Below these are 'External Links' for 'Configure Geo-Dash', 'Collect', and 'Project Dashboard'. The 'Export Data' section contains three buttons: 'Download Plot Data', 'Download Sample Data', and 'Download Shape Files', with blue arrows pointing to them. At the bottom, the 'Digital Object Identifier' section has 'Create DOI' and 'Publish DOI' buttons.

Figure 63. Place to export data.

Table 16. Summary of Output Files.

File Type	Purpose	Contains	GIS Display Type
SHP	Spatial geometry	Polygons only (without attributes)	Central points of plots with no disturbance or geometry of disturbance polygons
CSV	Form responses	Attributes only (no spatial extent)	Central points of plots with no disturbance or central points of disturbance polygons

Working with CEO Output Data in GIS

The full integration of both datasets is essential to ensure that spatial and attribute data are accurately linked and usable for spatial analysis.

To **merge** both sources into a single, **comprehensive geospatial layer**, they must be linked via a common field:

In the **SHP** file, the corresponding field is: **SAMPLE_INT**

In the **CSV** file, this key column is named: **sample_internal_id**

A custom **R script** has been developed to streamline this process. This script merges the attribute data from the CSV file (form data, represented as points) with the polygon geometries from the SHP file (spatial data without attributes).

The result is a complete geospatial layer, where each polygon contains all relevant form information. This unified layer enables more efficient analysis, visualization, and export in GIS platforms like QGIS.